

DOCUMENTATION OF ETHNOVETERINARY PRACTICES AMONG THE KOLAMS OF YAVTAMAL DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to compile the ethnoveterinary practices among the Kolam population. The Kolam dominant areas were selected for investigation. This unique ethnic group has diverse heritage and great ethnoveterinary knowledge. The total of 17 remedies were recorded. Some ethnoveterinary uses, which are quite interesting and additions to the existing knowledge. Total 32 plant species belonging to 22 families were recorded. These plant species need attention on account of their restricted availability, their threatened status and ethnobotanical significance.

Key words : Ethnobotany, Kolams, Yavatmal district

INTRODUCTION

The Kolamtribals are mainly found in Yavatmal, Chandrapur and Nanded district of Maharashtra, they are considered as most primitive tribal community of the district when compared to Gonds. The Kolams are considered in Dravidian group of tribes and ethnically and culturally akin of Gonds (Russel and Hiralal, 1973). Kolams are predominantly live in the interior zones of Mukutban, Zarizamani, Pandharkawada, Kelapur, Tipeswar reserve forest areas. Their independent unit or village is known as Pod. They believe their race originated during Pandav of great Mahabharat and they called themselves Pandavvanshi. Kolam community strongly believes in the indigenous knowledge of herbal treatments. Tattooing is very common among Kolams (Deogakar and Baxi, 2003; Vinatha Naini et al, 2013).

The use of herbal medicine is a first priority among them, they mostly depend on herbal

medicine for their health care, hence they approach the local healers known as Makulak for herbal medicine who have huge knowledge on use of medicinal plants. Kolam healers provide medicine in free of cost; a few of them sell herbs in the local weekly markets to get cash for their livelihood.

Ethnoveterinary medicine is based on folk beliefs, traditional knowledge, skills, method and practices used for curing disease and maintaining health of animals (Mc Corkle, 1986). People have easy access to modern veterinary facilities but still traditional remedies and traditional healers are their first choice. Ethnoveterinary practices are the holistic livestock health care management methodologies adopted by non-literature culture. These practices have been transferred from one generation to next generation orally. Due to lack of proper records and over exploitation of these plants by local people, the natural resources along with related traditional knowledge are reduced day by day (Roy 2003).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area:

The study was carried out Kolam dominant region of Yavtmal district. During the period of June 2013- April 2014. The present work deals with documentation of ethnoveterinary treatment from 15 tribal villages of Yavtamal District.

Survey:

The ethnoveterinary information was collected on the basis of interviews of villages and local traditional healers. Plant species were identified with help of floras, Cooke (1958), Naik (1998) and Singh and Karthikeyan (2000).

A data sheet was carefully prepared for documentation. The places selected for survey include rural as well as tribal areas. Locals were interviewed in most formal way. Personal details about informant were also entered on data sheet. Information like the name (common name, vernacular name and local name) of ethnoveterinary medicinal plants, the parts used to treat the animals and the mode of preparations were also noted down.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study total 32 plant species, representing 22 families have been enumerated for ethnoveterinary practices as remedy for 17 types of animal ailments. The most used plant part in preparation of formulation is mentioned. The herbal formulation were prepared afresh and administered both externally as well as internally. The majority of the formulation was prepared using a combination of plants. Traditional healers had their own method of herbal formulation and mode of applications. Along with wild plant and house old spices used in majority of formulation.

Moringa oleiofera for dog bite, *Lucas aspera* for scorpion bite are some of the note wording reports. Some healers distribute this medicine on some special days especially on Saturday. In most of the remote villages people rely only on local healers for their livestock health and do not prefer allopathic medicine.

The plants are enumerated alphabetically with their botanical name, family, local name and uses.

Enumeration :-

Acalypha indica L.

Family :- Euphorbiaceae

Local name :- Khokali

Uses :- The leaf paste with salt externally applied to heal the wound of goat, chicken and cows.

Achyranthesaspera L.

Family :-Amaranthaceae

Local name :-Aghada

Uses :- The root is hold at time of delivery for easy to discharge of embryonic envelop.

The root extract of the plant is given orally in case of dysentery.

Ailanthus excels Roxb.

Family :-Simaroubaceae

Local name :-Maharukh

Uses :- The bark juice of plant given orally in case of blood dysentery.

Annonasquamosa L.

Family :-Annonaceae

Local name :-Sitaphal

Uses :- The leaf paste applied on the wound. Used as antiseptic.

Bauhinia racemosa Lamk.

Family :- Caesalpiniaceae

Local name :- Root powder of *Bauhinia racemosa* with butter given to cattle against bone fracture.

Bombaxceiba L.

Family :-Bombaceae

Local name :-Katesavar

Uses :- Decoction prepared from bark of both *Bombaxceiba* and *Ficusracemosa* given to animal in case of retention of placenta.

*Boswelliaserrata*Roxb.ex Colebr.

Family :-Bursraceae

Local name :-Salai

Uses:- The mixture of bark of *Pongamiapinnata*, *Garugapinnata* and *Boswelliaserrata* is given orally in tympani.

Buteamonosperma (Lamk.)Taub.

Family :-Fabaceae

Local name :-Shimga

Uses :- The flowers of the *Buteamonosperma* given in indigestion of animal. 1 kg flowers are given to the animal for retention of placenta.

Calotropisgigantea (L.)R.Br.

Family :-Asclepidaceae

Local name :-Rui

Uses :- The latex mixed with red lead applied to treat wound .

Cardiospermumhelicacabum L.

Family :-Sapidaceae

Local name :-Kapalphuti

Uses :- The leaves paste of the plant mixed with water in case of tympani.

Cassia auriculata L.

Family :- Caesalpinaceae

Local name :- Tarval

Uses :- Tender shoot tip ground with butter and jaggery given to cure dysentery.

Clitoriaternatea L.

Family :-Fabaceae

Local name :-Gokarn

Uses :- Juice of the root is given orally in case of snake bite.

Seed are given with jaggery for relief in constipation.

*Coixlacryma-jobi*L.

Family :-Poaceae

Local name :- Ran maka

Uses :- Tuber of the *Coixlacryma-jobi* is given in case of tumour.

Coriandrum sativum L.

Family :-Apicaceae

Local name :-Sambar

Uses :- Whole plant mixed with fodder and fed to animal in foot and mouth disease. Fruit powder given to facilitate conception.

*Curcuma amada*L.

Family :-Zingiberaceae

Local name :-Ambehalad

Uses:- 1 teaspoon powder of *Curcuma amada* mixed with 100 gm of jaggery and alum given in tympani.

*Cuscutachinensis*Lamk.

Family :-Cuscutaceae

Local name :-Amarwel

Uses :- The stem mixed with fodder to increase the milk production.

Ferula asafoetida L.

Family :-Apiaceae

Local name :-Hing

Uses :- 100 gm resin of *Ferula asafoetida* mix with water given in orally to treat mastitis in cattle.

Lagenarialeucantha (Duch) Rusby

Family :-Cucurbitaceae

Local name :-Kadubhopala.

Uses :- Juice of leaves is given orally for expelling the worms.

Leucas aspera (willd.) Spreng.

Family :- Lamiaceae

Local name :-

Uses :- Leaf juice to cure wound and worm.

*Mangifera indica*L.

Family :-Anacardiaceae

Local name :-Amba

Uses :- The stem bark is put overnight in water and gives in diarrhoea.

Moringa oleifera Lamk.

Family :- Moringaceae

Local name :- Mungana

Uses :- bark powder with *Trachyspermum ammi*, Pepper and onion or garlic the paste given orally thrice a day given in dog bite.

Physalis minima L.

Family :-Solanaceae

Local name :-Gogala

Uses:- Whole plant of *Physalis minima* mixed *Coriandrum sativum* is given in case black quarter.

Phyllanthusvirgatus Forst.f

Family :-Euphorbiaceae

Local name :-Bhuiawala

Uses :- Leaves are mixed with green fodder and fed to animal to cure diarrhoea .

Pongamiapinnata (L.) Pierre

Family :- Fabaceae

Local name :- Karanji

Uses :- The leaves is burnt into ash; Ash paste mixed with coconut oil is applied on wound.

Puerariatuberosa (Roxb.exWilld.) DC.

Family :-Apocynaceae

Local name :-Bhuikoyra

Uses :- The plant cut into pieces mixed with equal amount of salt given in tympani.

*Solanumsurattense*Burm. f.

Family :- Solanaceae

Local name :- Ringani

Uses :- Fruit paste of *Solanumsurattense* given in case swelling of part of cattle.

Terminalia arjuna (Roxb.) Wt. & Arn.

Family :- Combretaceae

Local name :- Arjun

Uses :- The paste of stem bark of *Terminalia arjuna* applied over bone fracture.

Vitexnegundo L.

Fmily :- Verbenaceae

Local name :- Nirgudi

Uses:- The leaves of *Vitexnegundo* and *Cappariszeylanica* and soil boiled paste prepared is applied on fractured organ of the animal using wooden sticks during bone fracture.

Vignamungo (L.) Hepper

Family :- Fabaceae

Local name :- Mung

Uses :- The pulse of *Vignamungo* overnight soaked in water in given foot and mouth disease.

Withaniasomnifera (L.) Dunal.

Family :- Solanaceae

Local name :- Aswagandha

Uses :- Paste of the stem is applied on the skin for skin infection.

Wrightiatinctoria R.Br.

Family :- Apocynaceae

Local name :- Fetara

Uses :- The juice of the bark is given orally to destroy and expel out tap worms.

Zingiberofficinale Rosc.

Family :- Zingiberaceae

Local name :- Adarak

Uses :- The paste of tuber mixed with lemon juice applied on eye injury.

CONCLUSION

Kolam are the primitive tribal community of the district. Traditional knowledge of plants in this community is different because they preferably live in interior zones of forest areas. Traditional practices still remaining in villages. But the process of modernization this knowledge is vanishing very rapidly. Ethnoveterinary medicinal plants provide a cheaper treatment as compared to allopathic medicine and easily available and almost no side effect of this traditional preparation. Such information will be useful for phytochemist for further studies. The records indicate that there is an urgent need to conduct a detailed survey and also to promote measures for conservation of both the traditional knowledge and plants species.

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